

C-SCALE

D5.4 Blueprint, business and sustainability plan V1

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Deliverable Abstract

This document will provide an initial report on the procedure that other Copernicus platforms and EOSC e-infrastructure providers will have to follow to join the C-SCALE federation and description of engagement activities, key results and future plans beyond the life of the project.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and authorization infrastructure
AMB	Activity Management Board
C-SCALE	Copernicus – eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EAP	Early Adopter Programme
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GOCDB	Grid Configuration Database
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTC	High-Throughput Computing
OIDC	OpenID Connect
SRAM	Static random-access memory
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

The C-SCALE Project Blueprint, Business and Sustainability Plan v1.0 presents a summary of the strategic activities of the project. On top of the design and sustainability of new research data repository business models, the C-SCALE services are engineered to be independent from the lifecycle phase of the repository's development, the characteristics of the user community, and the type of data product this community requires (influencing the level of investment required in curating and enhancing the data).

The main goal of the C-SCALE project is to develop a solution that will simplify the utilization of Copernicus data and make it widely available through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

It will be achieved with the creation of the C-SCALE Federation, composed of:

- the C-SCALE Data Federation
- the C-SCALE Compute Federation

and empowered with Discover & Access services that make the C-SCALE approach unique in the universe of accessing the Copernicus data. The architecture of services will be enriched by Analytic Tools selected from the use cases requirements and users experience.

The figure below depicts the high level service design structure.

Figure 1: C-SCALE Service Overview

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The C-SCALE Data Federation is a federation of Earth observation product providers. Participating sites are federated in the following areas:

- User authentication, allowing for authenticated access to data at federation sites. In the context of C-SCALE, user authentication is used primarily for bookkeeping and usage statistics, not to restrict access to data, although even that is possible.
- Information system, publishing essential characteristics of sites in the federation. It is intended primarily for machine readability and relies on existing services available in the EOSC ecosystem, namely the GOCDDB.
- Product access protocols, whose choice is governed by existing usage patterns and compatibility with the authentication layer

More Details can be found in D2.1 C-SCALE Copernicus Data Access and Querying Design.

The C-SCALE Compute Federation brings together European EO data and infrastructure services, such as the commercial Copernicus DIAS or public providers like the Collaborative Ground Segments and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) computing providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support Copernicus research that deals with data-and compute-intensive workloads.

The Project adopted an innovative and flexible strategy looking towards the access to Copernicus and other Missions data, to develop a service and model approach based on the direct involvement of the user communities in the design of the C-SCALE federation (co-design) and the exploitation of the EOSC access models and interoperability standards (e.g. make the EO Data FAIR).

The federation is gradually shaped and consolidated through use cases design, support the development and onboarding, furthermore it is periodically revised and continuously improved accordingly. In the design of the federation the requirements to achieve a sustainable future are also properly taken into account.

Related to the sustainability of the federation, diverse business models will be analysed taking into account the current scenario in the European Research Area:

- EU and national or international public funding:
 - In the form of grants – partly funded by the EU and partly from other sources – that usually follow public announcements known as calls for proposals, subsidies managed by national and regional authorities and loans, guarantees and equity as forms of financial assistance to support EU policies and programmes
- Co- funding: contribution EU funding makes to a programme. It is expressed as a percentage of the total programme cost.
- Commercial model: commercial transaction between providers and users

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1 Introduction

This deliverable aims to present a blueprint and a business plan for the long-term sustainability of the C-SCALE service offering for scientists within EOSC and beyond.

The initial focus for C-SCALE is the setup of a federated data and compute environment that enables large scale research based on Copernicus and contributing missions data. One central element is the accessibility of a long-term data archive consisting of the total volume of the data acquired by the Sentinel mission since 2015 that is enriched by further satellite or in-situ data that is required to enable large scale analytics and proper validation of the results. Moreover, C-SCALE aims to facilitate the sharing of the research results following the FAIR principle to enable open and repeatable research.

The success of the C-SCALE federation depends on its openness and capacity to attract providers to extend its distributed setup, being so able to serve diverse and more challenging use cases. For this reason, C-SCALE is working on defining a federation model that shall encourage further providers to join the federation and therefore further increase the C-SCALE capabilities. This is pursued through the adopting of simple and standardised interfaces, like openEO, that simplifies the use of Copernicus data. Lowering the access barrier to the Copernicus data, C-SCALE will be able to wider use and inclusion of neighbouring research domains and facilitate cross-pollination of services and resources between adjacent research communities. The main objective for the C-SCALE is to complete successful the establishment of the C-SCALE federation and validate it with relevant use cases to create new services for the research. These new services will be part of the C-SCALE Federation catalogue and will enrich the EOSC service offer, opening up them to new research communities, together with the federation services for EO data exploitation

C-SCALE federation services and research services developed on top of them will be analysed in further details to investigate the opportunity to create a business and market perspective too. Next to the scientific applications of the federated C-SCALE service that will be accessible via the EOSC marketplace, within the EO domain and beyond, the C-SCALE Federation will have a special focus on measures to transfer research results towards operational services for the public and private sector.

This first version of the document will be focused on presenting engagement and collaboration model that can be used to encourage additional providers to join C-SCALE federation while the second version, expected for M27 (31st March 2023), will contain the full Sustainability and Business models based to the final available service catalogue.

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2 Blueprint

2.1 C-SCALE Federation

C-SCALE will leverage EOSC developments (e.g. the federated core) to make the unique data resources and body of knowledge of the Copernicus community accessible in a more harmonised way to new audiences and user communities through the EOSC Portal. It will deliver a modular, open, and robust federation for data discovery, processing and exploitation of Copernicus Data and, in general, EO Data. Details will be provided in further deliverables like: D1.5 Data Management (M18), D3.2 Compute federation optimised for Copernicus data analytics (M26) and D3.6 Periodical assessment of the services V3 (M24).

This open federation will integrate cross-/inter- disciplinary EOSC services, ensuring interoperability between distributed data catalogues, computational tools and infrastructure. It will also provide an open, well-documented framework for integrating new service providers and application developers.

C-SCALE will demonstrate that a shared, open, general purpose Copernicus access platform is feasible by combining/federating the best-of-breed tools, competences and services from DIAS, the national Collaborative Ground Segments and EOSC, delivering a consistent answer to user requirements, following the collaborative model of use cases as described below. By collaboratively building on the competences of pan-European e-Infrastructures and existing project initiatives, C-SCALE will federate European digital capabilities and lay the foundation for a five European open source Big (Copernicus) Data Analytics platform.

Since the C-SCALE federation is still in the process of being set up, the identified use cases that are deploying applications on C-SCALE are collaborating closely with the infrastructure providers to:

1. Co-design, test, pilot, refine and ultimately help create a federated infrastructure that delivers data and platform services that are useful for the community.
2. Deploy the use cases on available project of infrastructure, compute and data resources creating deployment recipes and templates for easier reuse later, thus creating a user-populated PaaS layer (see D3.1 deliverable).

The expected value and advantages of the innovative approach of the C-SCALE Federated Platform on top of the existing EO Platforms can be summarized in the following points:

- It will integrate data collected from satellite, ground-based, airborne and seaborne sources to create a very large, federated data infrastructure.
- It will offer a simple access and fast user query response to Big EO Data.

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- It will make the discovery, access and processing of these resources possible through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) relying on its discovery and access models and on its federated IT infrastructure.
- The offer of C-SCALE Services and Resources through EOSC will catalyse further innovative Earth Observation-based research and development activities and enable collaboration between adjacent communities. The co-design activities through pre-defined project use cases and open calls will streamline the integration of models, projects and programmes, with concrete production-ready pilot applications used to drive and validate the technical work.
- The C-SCALE Federation will also offer an improved mechanism for accessing the services, adding common policies, terms of use and privacy policy, developed on top of the EOSC ones, that works as a standardization level for the Federated Providers.
- Authentication and Authorization services are for free for the Federated members and included in the services offered in the Federation.
- The distributed architecture will improve the performances of the offered platform, in terms of reduction of costs, simplification of access, available capacity, reduced latency.

All the activities and developments listed are part of the engagement model and the effective co-design approach that will ensure the building of services on the actual necessities and requests of the users, considering filling up some gaps (like complexity in access the data) experienced in the past.

2.2 C-SCALE Data Federation

The C-SCALE Data Federation brings together Copernicus data providers from different ecosystems, e.g., ESA’s Collaborative Ground Segment, the Copernicus DIAS (Data and Information Access Services under the EC), independent nationally funded Earth Observation service providers and e-infrastructure providers. It starts off consisting of members in the C-SCALE Work package 2 but foresees inclusion of other partners identified either during the project (e.g., resource providers involved in other C-SCALE activities) or after its completion. The federation builds on the assumption that there are numerous, differently focused archives of Earth Observation data in existence, and while none of them can provide full global coverage, together they may be getting quite close to that goal.

Based on that assumption, C-SCALE is working towards two main goals:

1. Setting up a single interface for queries to look for datasets and products matching one’s needs. This will be based on a catalogue of EO providers joined in the federation, with a specification of their query and download endpoints, and their datasets and retention policies. This query interface is envisioned as open, STAC-based, and available to unauthenticated users. Aside of actual data providers, this approach will also be able to integrate 3rd party metadata services such as NextGEOSS, especially if they can already provide a STAC interface.
2. Providing federation-based, single-sign-on access to actual Earth observation products identified through the query interface or otherwise. This will federate C-SCALE Data

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federation members under EOSC AAI and enable access by interactive users as well as automated workflows furnished with valid OIDC tokens. As this is also the method of authentication envisioned for the C-SCALE compute federation and, indeed, the wider computing ecosystem of EOSC, it will be possible to use the same set of credentials to access C-SCALE data and compute resources and also have the latter impersonate entitled users when accessing the former. Unlike authentication, a centralized solution for authorization is *not* envisioned for the C-SCALE data federation. Local authorization settings at individual provider sites will supported, which is sufficient to fulfil specific bi-lateral agreements between providers of non-free products and relevant use cases. Authorization decisions will be made based on attributes (claims) brought in with users' OIDC tokens.

2.2.1 Joining the C-SCALE Data Federation

Partners willing to join the Data Federation will need to take the following steps:

- Expose a STAC query interface. Examples for stand-alone services and STAC<->OpenSearch adaptors will be provided by C-SCALE and used to implement STAC query interfaces for existing Data Federation members. Prospective members will be encouraged to reuse one of the provided solutions or deploy their own.
- Expose an HTTPS data access interface supporting federated authentication under EOSC AAI, enrolling as a service provider under EGI Check-in.
- Register their service in EGI GOCDDB, specifying the endpoints of their service and their data collection and retention policies. The format for machine-readable description of said policies will be determined in the following course of C-SCALE.

2.3 C-SCALE Compute Federation

The C-SCALE Compute Federation brings together computing providers to deliver a distributed infrastructure to support Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) use cases that deal with data- and compute-intensive workloads. The federation makes computing e-Infrastructure, potentially consisting of multiple services provided collaboratively by several service providers, accessible through homogeneous interfaces using a common AAI framework. Hence, C-SCALE facilitates the deployment of research applications that make use of Copernicus and other EO datasets, e.g. Sentinel-series satellite data, that are distributed across multiple providers.

C-SCALE Compute Federation offers access to two types of resources:

- Cloud: access to resources of the federation as IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) and container platforms (Kubernetes) with federated orchestration for the deployment of applications and platforms across providers in a seamless way;
- HPC and HTC: lightweight, federated and uniform access-integration layer to HPC and HTC systems.

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The two types of resources available in C-SCALE federation have different joining procedures.

The Cloud Federation relies as much as possible on the pre-existing EGI Federation to bring providers together as part of C-SCALE. EGI has well-defined procedure for onboarding new providers (PROC09¹).

This procedure ensures that providers meet all the policy and technical requirements for being part of the federation. PROC09 will result in the new provider fully registered in the EGI Configuration Database² with full contact information (e.g., site admin, security), with all the federation policies accepted and the minimum operational conditions to join are met (e.g. expected monthly availability and reliability, security coordination policies, etc.).

2.3.1 Joining the C-SCALE Compute Federation

The integration process can be summarized in the following steps:

1. Registration of the provider and endpoints in EGI GOCDDB.
2. Enable federated login to the cloud system by configuring EGI's Check-in in the provider's authentication services
3. Configure connectors to central EGI system to provide accounting and discovery information.
4. Ensure EGI's monitoring correctly checks the provider's services exposed to the federation. Monitoring is automatically enabled as soon as the endpoints are registered in GOCDDB.

Detailed information for OpenStack providers is available in EGI's documentation: <https://docs.egi.eu/providers/cloud-compute/openstack/>.

For providers joining the HPC and HTC federation, C-SCALE relies on the SURF Research Access Management (SRAM) service that provides common user access for the systems joining the federation. As with the cloud federation, C-SCALE reuses existing procedures from SRAM³ procedure. Connecting a service starts by registering the new provider with SRAM with information about the organisation, service details, contacts, service provider policies, SRAM collaboration connections and technical information. After processing the connection request for the service, SRAM will provide the provider with all the technical information on how to connect.

Registration within SRAM is not enough to access the resources, the provider needs to be coupled with a CO (Collaborative Organisation, the main important entity in SRAM that allows to link users to services) by a CO admin. First, an agreement is required between a CO, SRAM and provider so a service delivered by a provider can be used by a CO via SRAM. Once this agreement has been established the CO admin will be able to find the provider, can add the service to the CO and by

¹ https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/PROC09_Resource_Centre_Registration_and_Certification

² <https://goc.egi.eu/>

³ <https://wiki.surfnet.nl/display/SRAM/Connect+a+service+to+SRAM>

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doing so make it available to the members of that CO. Upon coupling the service to a CO, the technical integration will be enabled via LDAP for user management and access provisioning.

2.4 Interoperability between Data and Compute Federation

Interaction between the compute and data federation has been designed to simplify machine access for automated workflows. Both federations are themselves federated under a common identity federation (technically realized through EGI Check-in), recognizing the same credentials for the same users. That means that a user can use the same credential (typically the same ODIC access token) to instantiate resources in the compute federation and access products in the data federation.

Typically the user, or an automated workflow acting on their behalf in compute resources, instantiated in the compute federation, interacts with the Data federation in a way shown in the following picture:

Figure 2: C-SCALE Federation workflow

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The most important steps, having already instantiated resources in the compute federation, are:

1. Querying the data federation for products of interest. This is done through the C-SCALE Metadata Query Service (MQS), which exposes a STAC API and requires no authentication.
2. Staging matching products, that is, downloading the required EO products to local drive, which is suitable for use in actual processing/analysis. This requires authentication using the same identity (and token) used previously to instantiate compute resources.
3. Running the analysis on these locally staged copies of the EO products.
4. Optionally uploading the resulting products back to a Data federation member for redistribution – that is based on bilateral agreement between the use case and the user.

If the user so prefers, it is possible to perform all required download steps beforehand, and just perform the analysis then. It considerably increases storage space requirements at the compute providers' site, but some use cases may be designed to required that.

2.5 Use Case analysis

The research communities, through use cases, will co-design, test, pilot, refine and ultimately help to create a federated infrastructure that delivers data and platform services that are useful for the community.

At the end of the project, C-SCALE aims to have delivered a federation that enables users to generate meaningful results quickly and easily, by avoiding that users have to deal with the technical infrastructure details to get data processing and analytics pipelines to work. In other words, the complexity of using Copernicus, compute and storage resource provisioning and orchestration is abstracted away from the end-users, and C-SCALE will provide homogenous access to resources.

During the proposal writing phase of the project, 6 use cases were identified that will deploy workflows, processing Copernicus and EO data, to produce a result. These use cases are:

1. Aquamonitor: Detects land-surface changes
2. WaterWatch: Estimates reservoir water capacity
3. Land Surface Drought Analysis: Produces monthly seasonal drought forecasts
4. HiSea: Provides early warning for ports and aquaculture
5. RETURN: Determines forest recovery capacity
6. Wetland waterstress classification

These are complemented with the additional use cases identified through the open calls to broaden the community co-design beyond the project participants, additional use cases will be identified through the open calls. Call for use cases (<https://c-scale.eu/call-for-use-cases/>).

As a result, a series of recipes will be defined that could be reused to support a wide set of EO data analysis use cases. As mentioned, the C-SCALE Federation design is driven by user requirements to guarantee the delivery of an environment that satisfies user needs. User requirements are derived from deploying applications (use cases) on the C-SCALE federated infrastructure to test its usability

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and functional design. In doing so the use cases will provide feedback to the infrastructure providers on:

- ease of use of the resources,
- effectiveness of support,
- appropriateness of the technology,
- speed of access to resources and data,
- resultant usability of the application running on the federated infrastructure
- missing functionality/resources,
- satisfaction of the service/resource

Some of the challenges already identified while deploying the use cases are listed below. Note that the C-SCALE federation implementation is still ongoing, hence some of the challenges, e.g. authentication and authorisation, will be overcome once the C-SCALE federation components reach an operational status.

Challenges:

- **Harmonised Infrastructure as a Service.** Since there is no single European processing back-end that serves all Copernicus datasets of interest to the scientific community, and a monolithic infrastructure is not or will not be available in Europe, a federated infrastructure is considered to be the best way forward. A challenge here is to integrate the many heterogeneous cloud, HTC and HPC compute and storage providers. In C-SCALE, EGI Check-in and SRAM are used to authenticate and authorise users on cloud and HTC/HPC systems respectively.
- **A rich (but relatively low TRL) and heterogeneous ecosystem of platform services in Europe.** Many users make use of platform services offered by commercial providers such as Google, Amazon and Microsoft. These commercial providers have set a very high bar in terms of platform services. Their services are easy to access, easy to set up, and importantly the data is already there and close to compute. In deploying the use cases on C-SCALE, and in collaboration with the infrastructure providers, the project will create deployment recipes and (TOSCA) templates for easier reuse later, thus creating a user-populated PaaS layer.

Domain specific jargon. For example, “Argo”. Depending on who you talk to, Argo can be (1) a lightweight service for Service Level Monitoring, (2) a Kubernetes-native workflow engine, (3) a service to create machine readable data management plans or (4) a profiling float used to collect temperature and salinity data in the ocean.

A further challenge is related to data logistics. In deploying the use cases before the C-SCALE federation components are fully implemented, we needed to create local caches of the necessary data, meaning subsets of the data (in space and time) are created at each of the infrastructures supporting a use case. It is envisaged that the need for local caches will be removed once the data federation is in place. Challenges then arise related to whether or not the use case workflows handle data not being locally cached, and whether or not the network speed between providers will be fast enough to pull data from remote data infrastructures on the fly.

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3 Business and Sustainability Plan

C-SCALE business and sustainability plan aims to follow the approach adopted in EOSC. A deeper analysis will be conducted in the next months to develop an appropriate profit or non-profit strategy for business and will be completed in the next months. Early results are presented later in this section together with the engagement and collaborative models.

3.1 Engagement Model

EOSC is a federation of national, pan-European and thematic infrastructures. Its role is to interconnect these infrastructures so that each and every European researcher can benefit from the publications, data, software, tools, applications and services delivered by and for the research community at large. Supporting this mission, the C-SCALE Engagement Model is a framework that defines collaboration between the infrastructure providers and end-users in the context of Copernicus and Earth Observation data.

The focus of the engagement model is on the wants, needs and interests of the end-users as relevant for Copernicus and Earth Observations data processing and analytics, but also to engage all relevant stakeholders to co-design and deploy a Copernicus Data and Compute Federation where data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR).

As a project contributing to the EOSC establishment, C-SCALE adopted an engagement model aligned with EOSC and build on the EOSC-hub Communications and Stakeholder Engagement Plan (<https://www.eosc-hub.eu/deliverable/d31-communication-stakeholder-engagement-plan>).

The EOSC-hub Communications and Stakeholder Engagement Plan (hereafter referred to as Campos et al., 2018) maps the stakeholder landscape and identifies three roles: “user”, “provider” and “technology enabler”. Campos et al. (2018) note that stakeholders can be any of the three, or any combination of multiple roles. A given research community, besides having a user role, may be developing its own tools to enable certain services, in that sense a research community would have the role of technology enablers. The same holds true in the context of C-SCALE.

The below table provides an initial list of stakeholders and motivation for the C-SCALE project to engage with:

Table 1: Engagement Table

Stakeholder group	Main motivation for engagement. They...
EO infrastructures	... provide EO specific services, resources and technologies; Bring consumers; Enable the C-SCALE federation to function
E-infrastructures (Pan-European)	... provide EOSC services and resources; Bring consumers; Enable the C-SCALE federation to function
Research Infrastructures	...provide services and data; Bring consumers; Contribute to the C-SCALE data, platform and analytics layer

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ESFRI clusters	...are multipliers that bring service providers; Bring consumers;
Technology providers	... develop software that later on is used for service composition in the C-SCALE data, compute, platform and analytics layers.
H2020/Horizon Europe projects	...deliver services/technologies that can be relevant for inclusion in C-SCALE; They bring early-adopter user communities to the C-SCALE federation.
Scientific-service provider institutes	...are the most significant providers within certain disciplines (e.g. Mercator Ocean International), or towards specific groups (e.g. universities)
Business organisations	...can exploit services, data and technologies from the C-SCALE for commercial purposes; Contribute to C-SCALE with commercial services
Research communities (incl. Individuals and long tail of science)	...are the users or future users of C-SCALE services
Governmental, funding, policy agencies	...are funding the project and most of consortium members
General public	...are indirectly paying for the initiative so must be kept informed

The goal of the engagement model is to provide a mechanism to support user communities willing to use C-SCALE services and promote the inclusion of new service providers. Raising awareness on the existence of C-SCALE services, making them widely known to the user communities, gathering input from the researchers as to what is the usefulness perception of such services, and feeding that information to the providers implementing the C-SCALE federation teams is a fundamental task in the project.

The engagement instruments currently available include:

- A project website: <https://c-scale.eu/>
- A project twitter account: https://twitter.com/C_SCALE_EU
- A project wiki: <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/CSCALE>
- A Github organisation: <https://github.com/c-scale-community>
- An open discussion forum where the community can engage with the C-SCALE project to ask questions and share ideas and results. The forum can be found at: <https://github.com/c-scale-community/discussions/discussions> and the forum guidelines can be found at: <https://github.com/c-scale-community/discussions>
- An open call for use cases, where the community can apply for compute and data resources and platform services. The open call can be found at <https://c-scale.eu/call-for-use-cases/>

The engagement model, stakeholder landscape and engagement instruments will be updated in version 2 of the Blueprint, business, and sustainability plan.

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3.2 Collaboration Model

Establishing the C-SCALE Federation will offer an open environment, based on distributed services accessible through the EOSC Portal. The full framework of the C-SCALE Federation Rules of Participation and Acceptance Criteria, as well as the Business and Pricing models, are still under development.

The maturity of the services will include a full alignment of the Rules of participation and Acceptance Criteria with the EOSC ones. As part of this framework, we will have a clear, and hopefully automatic, testing feature to evaluate the resources of a potential federated candidate, specific agreement templates or SLAs, and everything that can give a comprehensive Collaboration Model overview of minimum requirements, performance targets and financial details.

The EOSC model will be reviewed as well to verify if applicable in terms of Business or Funding Model.

3.3 Business Model

A comprehensive and clearly defined Catalogue of C-SCALE services and resources is the starting point for the elaboration of the Business Model. At the beginning of Section 3, we stated that the C-SCALE Business model will follow the approach adopted in EOSC whenever possible. The C-SCALE Catalogue will be onboarded in EOSC so its services will be published in and offered through the EOSC Marketplace. To do that a number of verifications and agreements are needed, not only to define the services and the service components, but also to consolidate some fundamental information, like financial and legal aspects (who will constitute the legal entity, etc.), and more.

Although based on the EOSC one, the C-SCALE business model will be extended and tailored on the specific needs of an EO analytics platform and will leverage the advantages that the federated platform model could offer. Indeed, the Federate Platform model (like the C-SCALE Federation) facilitates transactions, reduces the costs, improves the accessibility of the services and the localization of available resources. Federated Data and Federated Cloud Platforms are considered as an ecosystem in the C-SCALE Federation, to be sustained by a combination of platform business models that create value by facilitating exchanges between two or more interdependent groups.

3.3.1 Business Model Through EOSC

The EOSC Portal serves as an entry point to EOSC services and resources from many domains by enabling users to access and request services supplied at institutional, national and regional levels enabling them to process and analyse data in a distributed environment. Services and resources are provided and maintained by different providers under a variety of licenses and access requirements (such as accessible by users outside its original community) described through a common template

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focused on value proposition and functional capabilities. Data preservation not only refers to the long-term storage of data, but also includes ensuring the preservation and maintenance of data, as well as its context, understandability, interpretability, authenticity and integrity.

The main goal for the C-SCALE services and the C-SCALE Federation is to ensure the service availability, in terms of capacity and support, after the completion of the Project. Some tests for self-service usage could be performed before the end of the Project, to simplify the offering model and to consider a more suitable SaaS, instead of the Platform approach based on managed interactions, as an option to be considered for service components part of the C-SCALE Federation.

Looking at the EOSC Business Models, two families of business models ('transactions' and 'learning – see webinar <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J7MewItLK8Q>), need to co-exist, potentially applied to different sides of the platform or targeting different clusters of roles and players, in order to sustain this model. Transaction-based models are widely known and built on the perceived value of the interactions between different entities. The Learning Business model in EOSC, seems less applicable to this case but more details will be evaluated later.

3.3.2 Service Offering

To define the offering model, it's necessary to identify the service components that can be ordered. In the EOSC approach summarized in the session above, the "services" are offered by each provider according to their commercial plan and pricing.

C-SCALE adopted the Virtual Access pricing model as requested by the INFRAEOSC-07 call and basic unit prices were agreed for the following components:

- Storage: TB/year or TB/Month
- Cloud IaaS: CPU/Year or CPU core/Month
- HPC/HTC: CPU/hour

The new services under development in the project, that will be offered in the C-SCALE Federation, will be managed under a new pricing model that is not completed yet. It needs more discussions and agreements between the providers and the federated Providers to set up a consolidated service offering on top of which a final pricing model will be defined.

In the EOSC approach, presented in the paragraph above, the aim to offer services free at the point of use, for researchers, it's reflected in the service offering categories described below:

- the services are offered fully open (for free or funded by projects)
- the services are offered by order to address any negotiation

In the C-SCALE case we could consider also the possibility to implement a hybrid model, in case the public funding percentage will be extended, or a commercial model, like pay per use can be added. Other options to be added to the pricing model, considering the co-design activity in the development of the services, could be included as per the example below:

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- the C-SCALE Federation can offer technical support to help the new provider/user to develop their new research application to the level of maturity (TRL) to become operational and generate income
- once a research application has reached the TRL needed for it to be operational and generate an income, it can then pay for the resources it consumes and support the sustainability of the C-SCALE federation.

3.4 Sustainability Plan

The first objective of the sustainability plan for the C-SCALE Federation will be to engage public entities and stakeholders, as described in the section 3.1, to ensure a proper continuity and long-term sustainability of the services. The release of the final C-SCALE Federation and related Business Model are conditional steps for a correct creation of the sustainability plan, that means that a future analysis will be needed for the actual C-SCALE Federation services offer.

The EOSC federated approach, as discussed above, can be part of this future analysis, considering the development phases EOSC is still following, to complete the steps below:

- The EOSC Sustainability activity will provide a set of recommendations concerning the implementation of an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation, to gradually open up its user base to the public sector and industry.
- Conduct an in-depth analysis of business models and their different implications in the choice of legal-entity, cost analysis, regulations, financial strategy and sustainability.
- The analysis would include an estimation of initial and longer-term cost projections.
- The proposed options accompanied with a sound risk analysis should be able to sustain, upgrade and scale the EOSC federation, as a whole and in its components. It should allow for alignment and convergence with national data infrastructures.
- The final model will be based on reliable mechanisms to ensure appropriate ongoing financial commitment by stakeholders and identify where funding responsibility lies for different components and services.

A full alignment between the Sustainability Plan and the Rules of Participation is a fundamental activity in the final C-SCALE Federation long term service offering, and it's currently a mandatory activity for the development of the federated EOSC platform, too. More analysis and criteria development will follow to describe a comprehensive set of models and plans, to support the Business and Sustainability approach in full alignment.

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4 Conclusions and future work

4.1 Status of Development and Completion of C-SCALE Federation

The development of the C-SCALE Federation and the related service catalogue will continue until the final assessment of the services in M30. At that time the full picture of the capabilities and achievements of the results of this project will be clear and the Federation implemented.

The integration of services in the final federated platform is the technical objective of infrastructure under construction. The new use cases that will be received, will play a fundamental role in co-design activities, not only to have clear feedback about the main topic to offer new answers to know issues in accessing the data, but also in updating the architecture in an effective way, to host all the needs registered by the users. On top of that, the work in selecting analytics tools, will allow the project to create an added value service, shaping reusable workflows that will make the discovery of the data and the accessibility to the requested Copernicus products, easier as expected.

4.2 Status of Development and Completion of Business and Sustainability Plan

With this first version of the Blueprint, Business, and Sustainability Plan, we have started a deeper investigation on the possibility to apply, totally or partially, the EOSC Business model to C-SCALE. The further development of C-SCALE services and the completion of the C-SCALE Federation will also clarify the offer and the access model, in order to better define the transaction model and the applicable pricing model to create a final Business model. Through the collaboration of the INFRAEOSC 07 Projects and EOSC Future, we will have the chance to test if the EOSC model will be appreciated, by various stakeholders and users, and to confirm the applicability for C-SCALE services.

On the other hand, collecting feedback that will request some changes or adaptation on the proposed commercial approach will help to consolidate the Business strategy of the C-SCALE Federation. A new engagement and communication plan will be available to reach a wider audience on the basis of the experience of the first year of project, the user forum, the dissemination of the C-SCALE newsletter, the audience registered in various events and direct feedback from providers. On top of C-SCALE Project activities, the participation to some special joint events, like EOSC Future resource providers days/clinics in April 2022 and May 2023, will drive us towards a more comprehensive verification of the EOSC model, or part of it, to be re-used in the C-SCALE Federation service offering and Business plan. Considering that all the main EOSC Stakeholders (all relevant research and innovation actors, including scientific communities, research institutions, learned societies, communities, national and European Infrastructures (generic or thematic), funders (public

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or private)) and the private sector (including data and journal publishers), will be reachable by these events, they will strongly contribute to the collection of ideas as well as the research community feedback, to assess further development and to consolidate the interest around the C-SCALE Federation. These interactions will act as a proper input for an effective Sustainability Plan.

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5 References and Reference Documents

Name	Link	Version
D2.1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5045317	1.0 (under EC review)
D3.1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5084884	1.0 (under EC review)
C-SCALE website	https://c-scale.eu/	N/A
C-SCALE Twitter	https://twitter.com/C_SCALE_EU	N/A
C-SCALE Wiki	https://confluence.egi.eu/display/CSCALE	N/A
C-SCALE user forum	https://github.com/c-scale-community/discussions/discussions	N/A

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